

Extraction Chromatographic Studies of Zirconium(IV) with High Molecular Weight Carboxylic Acid on Silica Gel

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A selective method has been developed for reversed phase extraction chromatographic studies of zirconium(IV) with high molecular weight carboxylic acid, Versatic 10, as a stationary phase on a column of silica gel. Quantitative extraction of zirconium has been achieved from acetic acid solution across the pH range 2.5–4.8. The effect of variables such as pH, stripping agents and flow rate on extraction and elution have been studied. Exchange capacity of the exchanger has been determined at different temperatures. Zirconium has been separated from a variety of elements.

THE high molecular weight carboxylic acid Versatic 9, Versatic 911, Versatic 10 have been widely used for the extraction of Ce^{IV} , Th^{IV} and U^{VI} .^{1,2} Extraction chromatographic studies of Zr^{IV} with TBP and dibenzoylacetone have been reported³. A survey of the literature reveals that these carboxylic acids have not been used for the extraction of Zr^{IV} by reversed phase extraction chromatography. We herein describe the use of Versatic 10 as a stationary phase on silica gel for the extraction and separation of zirconium from other elements. The method is simple, rapid and selective.

Experimental

A Elico LI 120 pH meter, ECIL GS 5700A spectrophotometer and chromatographic column (1 cm × 8.0 cm) of borosil glass were used.

Versatic 10, a mixture of high molecular weight, C_{10} , isomeric tertiary monocarboxylic acids was used as a liquid cation exchanger². A stock solution of Zr^{IV} (2.1 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared by dissolving $ZrO(NO_3)_2$ (AnalaR) in HNO_3 and diluted it to 100 ml with deionised water and standardised complexometrically⁴. A solution containing 150 μ g ml⁻¹ of Zr^{IV} was prepared by appropriate dilution.

Preparation of ion-exchanger: Silica gel (30–120 mesh; B.D.H.) was rendered hydrophobic⁵ by exposing it to the vapour of dimethyldichlorosilane in a nitrogen atmosphere for about 3 h then washed with methanol and dried at 100°. The gel was impregnated with Versatic 10 (diluted in benzene) and dried in a rotary vacuum evaporator to produce an uniform coating. Excess organic reagent present in the exchanger was washed off with 2M HCl. For column operation, the impregnated silica gel (5–6 g) was slurried with water and poured into the column. Each column can be used for at least 25 cycles without loss of extraction capacity. Exchange capacity of the exchanger was determined at different temperatures by measuring the number of milligram equivalents of sodium ion absorbed by 1 g of the dry

exchanger in the hydrogen form and was found to be 2.48 meq of H^+ /g at 30°.

Procedure: An aliquot of solution containing 150 μ g of Zr^{IV} was mixed with 0.2 M acetic acid (10 ml) and its pH was adjusted to 2.5 with 0.01 M NaOH or 0.01 M chloroacetic acid. The solution was passed through the silica gel column at a flow rate of 0.5 ml min⁻¹. Zirconium was extracted on the column and stripped with different mineral acids and salts. Solutions were collected into different fractions and the amount of Zr^{IV} in each fraction was determined spectrophotometrically⁶ with alizarin red S at 525 nm.

Results and Discussion

The extraction study of Zr^{IV} at pH 1.7–4.8 from acetic acid solution showed that Zr^{IV} was quantitatively extracted across the pH range 2.5–4.8. Flow rates of 0.5, 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0 ml min⁻¹ produced quantitative retention of zirconium on the column. The extraction behaviour of Zr^{IV} at different pH is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on extraction of Zr .

Stripping agents : The study of stripping of Zr from column with various mineral acids (Table 1) showed that Zr was completely stripped with 4 M HNO₃ and 6 M HCl. Sulphuric acid was not used for stripping as it interferes. Hence, for all practical purposes, 4 M HNO₃ was preferred as stripping agent. Incomplete stripping of Zr^{IV} was observed with acetic acid.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIOUS STRIPPING AGENTS FOR REMOVING Zr^{IV}

Zr^{IV} taken=150 µg, column=1×7.5 cm, Flow rate=0.5 ml min⁻¹, pH=2.5

Eluent	Concn. M	Peak elution volume (V _{max}) ml	Total volume of eluent (V _i) ml	Total recovery %
HCl	0.1	—	—	—
	0.2	25.0	50.0	15.0
	0.5	40.0	60.0	32.6
	1.0	20.0	40.0	43.3
	2.0	15.0	25.0	50.0
	5.0	6.0	12.0	86.6
6.0	4.8	9.6	101.2	
HNO ₃	0.1	—	—	—
	0.2	—	—	—
	0.5	20.0	40.0	21.8
	1.3	20.0	40.0	40.3
	2.3	15.0	25.0	57.3
4.0	7.5	12.5	100.9	
HClO ₄	1.0	10.0	20.0	20.2
	4.0	7.5	15.0	42.5
	8.0	4.0	7.0	75.2

Separation of Zr from binary mixtures : Zirconium was separated from binary mixtures by exploiting the effects of pH on extraction and also by differences in stripping characteristics. Ions which are not extracted by Versatic 10 at pH 2.5 from 0.2 M acetic acid solution pass through the column. Zirconium taken was stripped with 12.5 ml of 4 M nitric acid and analysed spectrophotometrically. In this way, zirconium was separated from V^V, Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ce^{IV}, La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Nb^V, Ta^V, U^{VI} and Th^{IV}. Zr^{IV} was separated from Cu^{II}, Hg^{II}, Pb^{II} and Al^{III}, which were coextracted under the recommended extraction condition by exploiting the differences in distribution coefficients at various concentrations of nitric acid. When a binary mixture of these metal ions containing Zr^{IV} was passed through the column at pH 4.8, the metal ions were quantitatively extracted. Cu^{II}, Hg^{II}, Pb^{II} or Al^{III} was stripped with 15 ml of 0.1 M HNO₃, followed by elution of Zr^{IV} with 4 M HNO₃. Zr^{IV} was separated from Fe^{III} by extracting both the elements at pH 2.5. Iron was eluted with 15 ml of 0.1 M HCl. Finally, Zr^{IV} was eluted with 4 M HNO₃. Ti^{IV} interferes in this extraction condition.

Separation of Zr from multicomponent mixtures : The extraction procedure was applied to the quantitative separation of zirconium from a number of the following multicomponent mixtures. Zirconium was separated from a mixture with Ce and Th by passing the solution through the column at pH 2.5; Zr was selectively extracted but Th and Ce passed through.

Zirconium was then stripped with 4 M nitric acid. The effluent containing Th and Ce, was passed through the column at pH 4.5, where both the elements were extracted. Th was stripped first with 0.2 M HNO₃, then Ce with 0.2 M H₂SO₄. A mixture of zirconium, thorium and uranium was passed through the column at pH 2.5 when only zirconium was extracted. Zirconium was stripped with 4 M HNO₃. The effluent containing Th and U was passed through the column at pH 4.5 to separate thorium from uranium. Later thorium was stripped with 1 M HNO₃. A mixture of Zr, Ce or Th and Fe was passed through the column at pH 2.5 when Ce or Th passed through. Fe was eluted with 0.1 M HCl followed by Zr with 4 M HNO₃. A mixture of Zr, Fe, Al and Cr was passed through the column at pH 3.8 when Cr passed through the column, Al was eluted with water, Fe with 0.1 M HCl and finally Zr with 4 M HNO₃. A mixture containing Zr, Cu, Zn and Hg was passed through the column at pH 4.8 when Zn passed through, while the other ions were retained. Cu was eluted with 0.01 M nitric acid, Hg with 0.2 M HNO₃ followed by Zr with 4 M HNO₃.

Elution behaviour of zirconium in multicomponent mixtures is given in Fig. 2 and the results are

Fig. 2. Separation of Zr from multicomponent mixtures.

summarised in Table 2. The separation of zirconium from Ce, Th and U is very important as they are associated with each other in various minerals, ores and fission products. The present method is very simple, rapid and selective. The total time required for each separation and analysis is about 2 h.

TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF Zr^{IV} FROM MULTICOMPONENT MIXTURES

Sl. no.	Cation	Weight added μg	Weight recovered μg	Recovery %	Eluent	Eluent volume ml
1.	Zr ^{IV}	150	146	97.3	4 M HNO ₃	12.5
	Th ^{IV}	100	97.5	97.5	0.2 M HNO ₃	25
	Ce ^{IV}	1 300	1 290	99.2	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	30
2.	Zr ^{IV}	150	148	98.6	4 M HNO ₃	12.5
	U ^{VI}	500	494	98.8	—	—
	Th ^{IV}	100	97	97.0	0.2 M HNO ₃	25
3.	U ^{VI}	500	498	99.6	—	30
	Ce ^{IV}	1 300	1 280	98.5	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	12.5
	Zr ^{IV}	150	151	100.8	4 M HNO ₃	—
4.	Th ^{IV}	100	98	98.0	—	17.5
	Fe ^{III}	100	102	102.0	0.1 M HCl	12.5
	Zr ^{IV}	150	151	100.8	4 M HNO ₃	—
5.	Cr ^{III}	20	19.8	99.8	—	20.0
	Al ^{III}	50	48.2	96.4	H ₂ O	15
	Fe ^{III}	100	102	102.0	0.1M HCl	12.5
	Zr ^{IV}	150	148	98.6	4 M HNO ₃	—
6.	Zn ^{II}	1 250	1 280	102.4	—	15.5
	Cu ^{II}	50	48	96.0	0.01 M HNO ₃	25.0
	Hg ^{II}	1 400	1 405	100.3	0.2 M HNO ₃	12.5
	Zr ^{IV}	150	148	98.6	4 M HNO ₃	—

Flow rate 0.5 ml min⁻¹; column 1 × 8.5 cm.

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References

1. A. K. DE and U. S. RAY, *Sep. Sci.*, 1971, **7**, 419; U. S. RAY and S. C. MODAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 38.
2. U. S. RAY and S. C. MODAK, *Sep. Sci.*, 1981, **16**, 87
3. A. N. TURANOV, Y. A. TAYLOR, A. M. REZNIK and I. N. KREMENSKAYA, *Radiokhimiya*, 1984, **26**, 292; K. UENO and M. KOSHI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1966, **39**, 2183.
4. F. J. WELCHER, "The Analytical Uses of EDTA", New York, 1967.
5. S. N. BHOSALE and S. M. KHOPKAR, 1979, **26**, 839, 1985, **32**, 155.
6. E. B. SANDELL, "Colourimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 3rd. ed., Interscience, New York, 1959.